

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (Perhumas) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Dorien Kartikawangi, Atma Jaya Catholic University of Indonesia

Abstract

The advancement of technological development has led to a revolution in the way people are communicating. This situation brings new value to industry and society in ways not possible previously, especially in relation to their contribution to the nation's reputation. The aim of this research is to analyse how public relations plays its role in building and maintaining a country's reputation. This paper is an example of conceptual thinking which uses a qualitative approach. Data is gathered by participant observation in developing strategic recommendations based on the organisation's experiences which were shared in the Public Relations Convention 2015-2018 held by *Persatuan Hubungan Masyarakat (PERHUMAS)* . the Indonesia Public Relations Association. It also includes interviews with high level management public relations officers. The results show that the Public Relations Association in Indonesia plays significant role in building and maintaining the country's reputation by its recommendations, implementation and evaluation which are addressed to government, company, media and PR professionals.

Keywords

communication; hyper-social organisation; public relations 4.0

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Introduction

Is it true that the role of public relations (PR) will be replaced by robots? Some people enthusiastically welcome technological innovations such as artificial intelligent (AI), machine intelligence (MI), virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR). These robots are now capable of providing news content and of performing various tasks. Artificial intelligence capabilities are developing fast and are threatening various professions including public relations. While technological development is welcomed, it also creates worries for those who may not be ready or who do not understand the strategies underlying its use. The strongest challenge faced by the public relations professionals is their lack of knowledge and skills in facing the rapid development of technology. Those two matters are really important for supporting public relations activities: analysing capability, planning the communication strategy up to its implementation and evaluation. While the presence of big data is considered as valuable in analytical activities, public relations professionals still need to improve their capability in taking advantage of big data.

As human beings, PR professionals have their own intelligence in developing optimism. Attributes of human intelligence which can not be found in machines include reasoning, empathy, and emotion. Such conditions are the strength of public relations professionals which need to be sharpened and developed. This view is based on a recent study concerning the improvement of human resources in communication and particularly in public relations (Kartikawangi & Sarinastiti, 2014; Kartikawangi, Temaluru & Unaradjan, 2016; Laksamana, 2014; 2018).

As the association of PR professionals, the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) plays an important role in developing the conceptual and practical presence of public relations. *Perhumas* conducted several activities aimed at improving competence via coffee morning events by providing some relevant topics which were guided by resource-persons, accreditation, certification, and convention related to national public relations.

This paper presents some conceptual thinking based on the organisation's experiences. The paper pertains to the events around the National Convention on Public Relations (Konvensi Nasional Hubungan Masyarakat/KNH) that is conducted annually by Indonesia PR Association (Persatuan hubungan masyarakat/Perhumas). The topics of KNH focussed on PR strategies needed to face global, regional and national challenges. This study focused on the events of the National Convention on Public Relations during the last four years, from 2015 to 2018. Primary data were collected based on participatory observation and secondary data were taken from the documents of National Convention on Public Relations. The historical tracks of the convention was then used as the material of discussion to visualise the presence of hyper-social organisation and public relations 4.0 in Indonesia on how PR strategies have helped to prepare to face these challenges. Recommendations are addressed to the government, company, media and PR professionals.

The National Convention on Public Relations Journeys 2015-2018

Jakarta, 2015: Public Relations Journey, the Sustainable Path to Trust & Reputation!

In the last 10 years, the function of PR in Indonesia has not reach its optimum objective in the aspects of capability and quality. In addition, there is the gap in the

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

government public relations officers which does not keep up with the dynamics of content. Government PR officers are not considered capable in applying digital technology nor in its English language capability. It is difficult for Indonesia to avoid ASEAN economic social impacts. Regulation is still traditional while the market is rapidly evolving. The competitiveness of human resources in the field of public relations is relatively lower and is predicted to be less-competitive than foreign resources.

From the perspective of the Indonesian government, public relations is already conducted transparently and the president of the Republic of Indonesia always updates the public on governmental issues. Public relations officers as the nation-guardians play a role in keeping the trust of stakeholders. The presidential media-team plays the public relations well. Public relations is capable of building mutual understanding between institutions and the public in order to maintain good partnerships in the long term.

Indonesia needs public relations because there are opportunities. Public relations is needed by both for government and private institutions. Therefore, public relations professionals must work professionally. PR has to be able to develop and even maintain reputation, develop image as well as develop public trust. To allow the company to survive, public relations must provide its best services, must hold the code of ethics and keep the soul. Therefore, a theoretical basic is not enough and must be accompanied by improvisation. It is hoped that public relations can play an important role in the country's activities and unify the nation. In this regards, public relations should know the public's expectations and provide education to these publics.

From the industrial perspective, public relations must be capable of attracting investors and businesspeople in order to encourage investment in Indonesia. To meet such an aim, public relations must master clear communication, meaning not merely forwarding information but also creating content and gaining useful feedback. One of some challenge faced by public relations officers is to compete with other officers who having professional background other than communication.

The required competency of public relations officers among other are: capability to choose the presentation content as well as to conduct presentations well; capability to choose recent relevant content, to have high integrity and understand the openness of public information. In this context, media and social media cannot be separated from the role of public relations where media relations should work alongside of and be part of strategic communication. Public relations must understand the characteristics of media and social media, such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube and so on. and take advantage in accordance with characteristics of each social media.

Based on the discussion, the recommendations of KNH 2015 are as follows:

- *Perhumas* has to forward its opinion concerning the roadmap of Indonesian public relations.
- Public relations must be proactive in developing stakeholders networks through public relations activities.
- Collaboration with similar organisations including governmental institutions, universities and industries, provides innovative contributions via new ideas to enable public relations professionals to become more concrete and

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

appreciated by management as a strategic function, to be involved in finding quick solutions with the aim of supporting steps to its members as well as to government in order to realise its programs.

2.1.2 Bandung, 2016: The power of PR: Building Indonesia's reputation 2030

According to the World Economic Forum, the position of Indonesia in the 2018 Global Competitiveness Index is already significant. In 2014, Indonesia was ranked at 119th and by 2016 it had reached 47th and then developed to be ranked in the top ten (<http://reports.weforum.org/global-competitiveness-report-2018/country-economy-profiles/>). A revolution in social habits has been the main cause in addition to Indonesian culture. Positive thinking has significantly influenced the index ranking and such conditions are supported by the role of public relations in building up a good national index via governmental works and the role of mass media.

In the context of building global trust, we cannot merely be supported by socialisation but three aspects must be in place. The first step as a citizen is to create self-confidence focused on three aspects: attitude, speaking your mind, working harder. This should be followed with self confidence to undertake a regular act which may seem to be irregular one. It is well known that the most expensive value is trust. The ultimate action for an institution is to seek the trust of the customer and also get suitable certification. Then, the capacity of market-target in Indonesia must be optimised from a domestic perspective, and therefore capability will build-up global trust.

Digital innovation, means that an ample amount of innovation will assist Indonesia on the world stage. Such conditions can be actualised by pushing pre-startup to become vlogger players. Startups in Indonesia must be supported until they reach world level. On this matter, several issues shall be mentioned:

- Digital innovation is the key for public relations and marketing to bring Indonesia to the world forum.
- The startup activist must be supported continuously to innovate because they are key to moving Indonesia toward world-digital map.
- To maximise the function of corporate communication, GMD employees, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and a board of directors or management board is essential in order for a company to be dominant.
- Other strategies must be implemented to build company reputation by engaging customer trust, strategic partnerships, capacity building, collaboration building and watching the national and international market target.

The challenge of the public relations profession is to face the changes in the 21st century. To build-up reputation, the implementation of the business good community and country can become the mainstay. Unique principles plus craftsmanship can be used as the foundation of nation building characteristics, as at present, there is too much privacy and there needs to be more openness at a public level. The role of public relations in national character building is activated through educating the public.

Even though the public relations profession is not one that will face tight competition within ASEAN economic region, this condition needs to be considered in

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

order to anticipate the current globalisation movement. These matters need to be considered as follows:

- a. wherever the organisation appreciates the importance of public relations and if this is affecting the organisational objectives;
- b. if public relations is functioning well, is this resulting in improved communication?;
- c. do public relations professionals have an adequate level of education? Empowering public relations officers within an organisation is crucial. The recent phenomena indicates that there are many public relations officers who are selected without a background in the public relations discipline, such as journalists, marketing and other disciplines. This needs to be considered in light of gaining a more professional officer;
- d. formal education in public relations is not sufficient in order to become a good officer and further enhancement is needed while he/she works as public relations officer.

Related to developing human capital in public relations, the government supports building Indonesian public relations by providing regulation on standardised competence for a public relations officer that is designed to provide human resources capability to contribute in the case of crisis-management. Public relations standards are regulated in *Peraturan Menteri Komunikasi dan Informatika No. 12 Tahun 2015 tentang Standar Kompetensi Jabatan Fungsional Pranata Hubungan Masyarakat* (<http://jabatanfungsional.com/standar-kompetensi-jabatan-fungsional-pranata-humas/>), and includes three important aspects which have become the focus in recent times: environmental issues, crisis management, and reputation management. Meanwhile the Indonesia PR Association held workshop and accreditation program for PR professionals in order to standardise the competencies.

In terms of behaviour and actions, public relations officers have the following roles: nation character building, creating agenda setting and liaison and bridging (solution) to many problems. The importance of public relations is to develop knowledge and standards that impact rapidly in the democratisation of the political system and enhance the era of openness and egalitarianism. The profession of public relations is of strategic importance as its profession is open for all.

Public relations is about reputation and includes behaviours, abilities, and skills. A public relations officer can be competent and professional after gaining new audiences, new relations, new tools, and new standards. These four scopes are part of the transformation required in Asean economic society. There are three public relations insights in ASEAN: build important relationships, endorse friendships, build a good image. This is followed by regional understanding or cross cultural regional, critical thinking and strategic thinking, media strategies and digital engagement, history and political structures, language and lobbying. The basic requirements of a public relations officer include: a good attitude, an understanding of human ego; the ability to create a good impression; the ability to develop an attractive personality; the ability to listen and read: the ability to be community savvy and to practice and criticise without offending; and certification standards and roadmaps.

How can PR officers play their role in maintaining a good reputation? This can be assisted by a public relations strategy: *One Look* (wonderful internal

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

communication), *One Voice* (orchestrating external communication) and *One Person* (winning acknowledgement). How is such a strategy developed?

One look, means how Indonesia highlights its performance and means its communication strategy shows that the society thinks Indonesia has *one* (one look).

One voice, means that Indonesia agrees to be one group which in this context refers to Unity in Diversity, that it is always digitally coordinated, and which all matters concerning digitalisation are broadly accepted. With this in mind, Indonesia endeavours to be accepted externally.

The important role of society as PR and vice versa, is a part of one look. This consists of several parts: the most effective spokesperson and the best ambassador is used in every single area. Indonesia PR Association initiated as well as lead this strategy and it is implemented by its members all over Indonesia as agents of change.

The KNH 2016 discussion summarised that from the company's perspective, the company shall more fully focus on the people. How to get invoice? Companies usually find rumours about the company originate externally not internally. Therefore before such information becomes external, the discussion suggests that organisations communicate information to its employees. There are three forms of employee engagement which may develop through communication programs: culture, change and transformation. This matter leads the transformation process and cultural change working towards a world class company. Examples would include young volunteer workers in units that conduct routine activities to improve employee engagement, employee engagement activities up close and personal with inspirational figures, knowledge sharing, voluntary activities and so on.

The main idea is how to put Indonesia in world forum via developing its international reputation. Some ideas include learning from the experiences of several companies in improving reputation via internal empowerment and developing a company's reputation by strengthening internal factors. It is a challenge to make public relations an open profession as the term in Indonesia means all people can achieve success in an occupation.

Other questions include how to raise Indonesia global reputation, how to improve competence in public relations and thus make a significant contribution to improving the country's reputation that includes digital innovation. Based on the above-mentioned questions, the KNH 2016 made recommendations as follows:

- Public relations must show positive thinking;
- Public relations must communicate nation building character;
- Public relations must be agenda setting;
- Public relations must embrace digital innovation.

Bogor, 2017: #IndonesiaBicaraBaik (#IndonesiaSpeaksWell)

Observation undertaken by the Indonesia PR Association shows that there are many people who did not yet understand the role and function of public relations while media transformation is moving quickly and needs improvement in public relations. In this context, each Indonesian citizen is a vehicle for public relations for their country thus in such a role as they must project a positive message to the public to create trust and reputation for their organisation and country. The function

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

of public relations is not merely the responsibility of communication professionals, but is the responsibility of all citizens. Building trust and reputation must be done consistently and sustainably. Based on these conditions, the KNH 2017 forwarded a theme #IndonesiaBicaraBaik (#IndonesiaSpeaksWell) with the aim of educating the society in understanding their own role and function as public relations practitioners.

In brief, the discussion about #IndonesiaBicaraBaik as conducted in KNH 2017 is a response to how to build trust and reputation which must be done consistently and sustainably. Development and media transformation happens rapidly and needs rapid implementation of public relations in line with the rapid development of society and journalism. Therefore, public relations needs to be capable to do data-processing and word-processing to build trust and dialogue. Information can be achieved easily from anybody using any media in real time and in this case, the public is a critical source. In this regard, public relations needs to be capable of listening and creating better dialogue for the purpose of learning the trend of mass and social media with the last aim to develop trust and reputation. The traffic of information is getting faster and is creating anxiety. Hoaxes can be easily shared.

Such hoaxes cover positive news and well known Indonesian achievements, and for this reason, Indonesian public relations must start the movement #IndonesiaBicaraBaik. Think before sharing must be one of our guidelines. The public must be aware that they play a role in the public relations for Indonesia. Recently there have been negative content on social media despite the existence of many positive achievements that could have been highlighted. Therefore, the government and *Perhumas* has made a call for action for society to share positive stories to create optimism among the Indonesian populace. The government decided that 2017 was an investment year for Indonesia, in this regard, public relations and media play their important role. At present, the Indonesia economy is moving from commodity-oriented to services-based where one of its sectors is public relations in the area of communication media. The government and *Perhumas* are working together in designing a corridor. Mutual coordination is needed with the hope that the Indonesia Public Relations Association can begin cooperation and coordination between the two which will provide a blueprint for the future program of *Perhumas*. The press is an important partner of the Indonesian economy because the it can publicise Indonesian achievements and creating confidence within Indonesian society to allow it to visualise a more advanced society within the next 10 years, up to the year 2030. Possible achievements include:

- Research conducted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) in 2019 shows that Indonesia will be ranked 6th in the world economic rankings by 2023. In the next four years, the financial agency predicts Indonesia's economic growth can reach 5.4%, market share 2.8% and gross-domestic-product (GDP) per-capita US\$ 5.120 (IMF, 2019). By 2030, Indonesia will have demographic bonus, where the productive ages will reach twice than non-productive ages and in the next 12 years the Indonesian economy will become an economic powerhouse in the world
- The government produces 16 regulation package making all permits available online. The objective of such regulation is to make business matters and permit issue easier.
- The government will determine special economic zones to allow Indonesia to become ranked 3rd in terms in world investment.

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Fake news or hoaxes will disappear if journalism can find and describe the factual information. In this regard, media must work hard to find out such site-finding because there is the site of credibility, writing down in detail based on texture can be the solution of any debate.

The National Convention on Public Relations (2017) published the following recommendations:

- Start the movement #IndonesiaSpeaksWell in order to create public awareness of the importance of good public relation for Indonesia
- Think before sharing must become one of Indonesia's guidelines
- Public relations must be capable of processing data and information in order to build a strong foundation of trust and ongoing dialogue.
- Build coordination between the public relations organs of similar organisations to ensure that the same agenda is followed.

Jakarta, 2018: Public Relations 4.0

We are now in the era of 4.0 in which many changes are occurring in many sectors including banking, financial, marketing and journalism. Many professions are predicted to be replaced by robots (Frey & Osborne, 2013). However, it is debatable, whether the PR profession will suffer this fate although it may be replaced by robot artificial intelligence according to Frey and Osborne (2013) who have examined how susceptible jobs are to computerisation. According to their research, PR specialists have an 18% chance of being replaced by computers in the next 20 years (Martek, 2019). In the 4.0 era, widespread smartphone use by the larger public is a form of media. Those in the public with more than 10,000 followers is media. Robots can make their own news, even artificial intelligence can be the news reader. News can be produced independently without censorship and this can result in the public not being able to distinguish credible from fake news.

In his speech for the opening of Indonesia Industrial Summit 2018 (4 April 2018), HE President Joko Widodo outlined the efforts of his government to revitalise Indonesian industry as a whole. The aim is to create work opportunities and inclusive growth for all levels of the economy in such a program. The external challenges relating to the rapid development of information technology and communication also needs the public relations role to proceed. Innovative transformation needs to be sustainable and needs to commit to wider society. The government launched Roadmap of National Industry Development under the brand *Making Indonesia 4.0* therefore, in this roadmap, Indonesian public relations needs to be developed to be Public Relations 4.0. At the same time in order to advance efforts to lessen the expertise gap, the government, private and education institutions need to create a blueprint PR 4.0 as its basic guidelines for the future.

There are two strategies proposed by the resource persons in KNH or National Convention on Public Relations 2018: the need of creative content creators and storytellers capable of promoting the public relations message or public relations digital era (PR 4.0) via online media or/and social media. While PR regularly uses digital media, this communication medium needs to become its mainstay. Therefore, supporting Galloway and Swiatek (2018) research findings, this does not imply that PR practitioners need to become expert technologists, rather, PR should develop a sufficient understanding of AI's present and potential uses to be able to offer informed counsel.

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Based on the above-mentioned points, KNH 2018 recommends as follows:

- Character:
 - a. Public relations 4.0 has many characters i.e. adaptive, global thinking, creative, digital, quick, responsive, agenda setting, collaborative and non sectoral ego.
 - b. Public relations 4.0 absolutely must own a precise character to defend the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia.
- Competency:
 - a. To support the Roadmap Making Indonesia 4.0, PERHUMAS will launch ~~Public Relations Accreditation 4.0q~~
 - b. To improve digital-based soft skills.
 - c. The government must regulate a mandatory set of public relations duties for professionals who must pass the accreditation and competency in the 4.0 era.
- Collaborations:
 - a. Public relations 4.0 shall have collaborative spirit which means inter-instituional communication for government, private as well as educational institutions accepting the principles of strategic communication for unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia.
 - b. To improve company synergy between companies, government and educational institutions to provide professional public relations by mapping the expectations of business partnership and to synchronise a curriculum suitable for the millennial generation as the effort to gain capable public relations practitioners in accordance with the needs of stakeholders.
- Public Relations Code of Ethics:
 - a. In the era 4.0 *Perhumas'* code of ethics must be revised in accordance with era 4.0.
 - b. Public relations professionals must have moral integrity and high commitment to the profession.
 - c. Public relations professionals must review the Public Relations Code of Ethics to understand the role and function of public relations.
 - d. Public relations professionals must follow *Perhumas'* code of ethics
- Policy:
 - a. Particularly for government public relations, the government shall put the public relations in the priority position.
 - b. It is hoped that the government will publish regulations in accordance with the developing era. Such policy is in line with the movement #IndonesiaSpeaksWell

Conceptual thought from the journey of National Convention on Public Relations

Velasco (2018), chair of the Global Alliance for Public Relations and Communication Management, suggested ten trends that will affect the exercise of communication. These are: the pressure for greater transparency, the search for authenticity, the growing importance of corporate purpose, good stories (well told and with a socially responsible purpose), the micro-video boom, the omnichannel, the entertainment factor, cooperation with other functions, accreditation of the value of communication. His synthesis relates to and supports the PerhumasqKNH discussion.

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Bottom of Form

Understanding the journey of the National Convention on Public Relations over the last four years, it can be seen that there is red line between such topics each year. The red line also shows how the national and global situation influence the profession and role of public relations. From the perspective of public relations professionals, building stakeholders trust and reputation is their main focus. To speak from a wider scope as a citizen, building national reputation at the international level can also be their responsibility.

The state's situation is an important area that needs to be considered in public relations. These considerations include social, politics, economy, culture, defense and security. Considering the heterogeneity of Indonesia, unity is a matter that must be maintained. In the development of information technology and communication particularly social media, where the individual is an information producer and consumer as well (prosumer), it is known that awareness about the impact of what s/he states in social media can be positive or negative. The role of PR in guarding unity is needed until the occurrence of idea on social movement #IndonesiaBicaraBaik.

Figure 1. KNH Journeys

A country is an organisation that is also influenced by and influences its environment, similar to a company. Advancements in technological development has led to a revolution in the way that people are communicating. Social media is a massive participation platform that allows the hyper-social wave to sweep across everyone . employee, customers, prospects and detractors . on a scale that is beyond anything that we've ever seen before (Gossieaux & Moran, 2010). In effect, social media gives everyone a voice equal to that of a company. Internally, this participation platform is changing the companies work. No longer are communications limited to the channels of the traditional command-and-control hierarchy. People now find ways to communicate and help one another across conventional reporting structures. Externally, the impact of this platform is not all that different from the internal impact. People can behave the way they were hardwired to behave in the first place . humanly and tribally.

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

Such conditions also happen in the context of a nation state. The KNH journey and recommendation proposed for every result of KNH provides in essence all of the PR 4.0 characteristics that need to be continuously developed starting from individuals as PR professionals to member of the state and the world. The characteristics of PR 4.0 and its contribution to the country can be seen in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2. Indonesia Public Relations 4.0

Conclusion

In the context of hyper-social organisation and the advancement of technological developments, public relations professionals must improve themselves continuously and enhance their competence particularly when facing the development of communication technology and information, Public relations competence must be balanced with basic ethics to enable watch clearly what shall be done and shall be avoided includes its impacts. Playing the role as a creative content creator and storyteller, public relations professionals might also play their role to increase the nation's reputation, guarding unity and contributing ideas for government policy. In particular, PR should develop a sufficient understanding of AI's present and potential uses to be able to offer informed counsel. Furthermore, besides the individual role of PR professionals, there is also a significant role for the PR association in building and maintaining the country's reputation.

Based on these conclusions, formal research on PR competence is needed by companies and the nation in the 4.0 era and should be done with multiple strategies and mixed methods in order to gain validity and reliability. Therefore, such curricula in PR higher education and certified workshop may need to be developed to meet the requirement of standardisation.

Acknowledgement

Upon the publication of this paper, the author would like to express appreciation to the Chairman, Agung Laksmiana, and all members of research and competencies

The role of the Indonesia Public Relations Association (*Perhumas*) in building and maintaining the country's reputation

division, Indonesia PR Association (*Perhumas*): Mulharneti Syas, Dian Budiargo, Zulkarnin, Fardila Astari, Rini Adiati dan Luciana Budiman, as well as Anggia Bahana Putri, the executive secretary of *Perhumas* in providing documents, and also to Bambang Suprihadi as the academic writing support.

References

- Frey, C.B., & Osborne, M.A. (2013). The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation? Available from https://www.oxfordmartin.ox.ac.uk/downloads/academic/The_Future_of_Employment.pdf.
- Galloway, C., & Swiatek L. (2018). Public relations and artificial intelligence: It's not (just) about robots, *Public Relations Review*, 44(5), 734-740.
- Gossieaux, F. & Moran, E. (2010). *The hyper-social organization*, New York: McGraw Hill.
- International Monetary Fund (2019, March 7). Indonesia and the IMF. Available from <https://www.imf.org/en/search?q=Indonesia%20rank%20on%20economic%202019&sort=relevancy>
- Kartikawangi, D. & Sarinastiti, N. (2014). *The knowledge, skills, capability and personality which are needed in communication work*, Yogyakarta, Indonesia: ASPIKOM
- Kartikawangi, D., Temaluru, Y. & Unaradjan, D. (2016). Cross cultural communication competency in business interaction: A theoretical study, *Cross Cultural Communication Conference Proceeding*, Bangkok, Thailand: Chulalongkorn University.
- Laksamana, A. (2014). *What CEO Wants from PR*. Yogyakarta, Indonesia: B-First
- Laksamana, Agung (2018). *Public relations in the age of disruption*. Yogyakarta, Indonesia: B-First.
- Martek, Martija, PR automation: Will robots replace PR people? Retrieved from <https://prowly.com/magazine/pr-automation-will-robots-replace-pr-people/>
- Peraturan Menteri Komunikasi dan Informatika No. 12 Tahun 2015 tentang Standar Kompetensi Jabatan Fungsional Pranata Hubungan Masyarakat, Retrieved from <http://jabatanfungsional.com/standar-kompetensi-jabatan-fungsional-pranata-humas/>
- Public Relations National Convention (2015). [unpublished documents]
- Public Relations National Convention (2016). [unpublished documents]
- Public Relations National Convention (2017). [unpublished documents]
- Public Relations National Convention (2018). [unpublished documents]
- Velasco, J.M. (2018). Challenges-and Trends for PR in 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.globalalliancepr.org/thoughts/2018/12/13/challenges-and-trends-for-pr-in-2019>.
- World Economic Forum, Global Competitiveness Index, Available from <http://reports.weforum.org/global-competitiveness-report-2018/country-economy-profiles/>.